

Yield loss per unit increase in damage by GM, YSB, and LF in five rice varieties at 3 growth stages during 2 seasons.^a Madurai, India, 1988-89.

Variety	Yield loss (%)					
	Tillering		Panicle initiation		Maturity	
	Season I	Season II	Season I	Season II	Season I	Season II
<i>Gall midge (GM)</i>						
IR20	9.0	14.0	4.0	3.0	—	—
ADT36	1.0	3.0	2.5	2.0	—	—
MDU3	0.5	1.0	0.5	1.0	—	—
Sona	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	—	—
IET9689	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	—	—
<i>Yellow stem borer (YSB)</i>						
IR20	3.0	8.0	2.0	7.0	1.0	13.0
ADT36	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	2.0	2.0
MDU3	0.5	1.0	0.5	1.0	0.5	1.0
Sona	1.0	2.0	2.0	4.0	1.0	1.0
IET9689	8.0	1.0	12.0	1.0	4.0	2.0
<i>Leafhopper (LF)</i>						
IR20	2.0	2.0	3.0	3.0	10.0	10.0
ADT36	5.0	14.0	3.0	13.0	7.0	10.0
MDU3	4.0	6.0	3.5	3.0	4.0	2.0
Sona	2.0	4.0	4.0	4.0	0.5	1.5
IET9689	5.0	0.5	1.5	0.5	3.0	1.0

^aSeason I = Jun-Sep 1988, season II = Oct 1988-Jan 1989.

maximum loss from GM infestation in both seasons. GM-resistant MDU3 suffered the least damage from GM and YSB.

YSB caused heavy losses during the second season in all varieties except

IET9689, which suffered more during the first season. LF incidence accounted for heavy loss in ADT36 and MDU3 during early crop growth stages and in IR20 at later stages. □

Resistance to rice thrips in breeding lines derived from *Oryza officinalis*

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Fifty breeding lines derived from *O. officinalis* were exposed to natural infestation by thrips *Stenchaetothrips biformis* (Bagnall) during August 1990 at the ACRI, Killikulam.

Each breeding line was sown in 3 rows of 5 m each and susceptible TN1 and resistant Ptb 21 were sown at random. The breeding lines were not replicated in the preliminary screening test. When the susceptible TN1 showed a rating of 9, all breeding lines were rated for thrips damage using 0-9 scale. Breeding lines that showed a damage rating of 1 in the preliminary screening test were retested in a randomized block design replicated five times. Damage

rating was done as described. Of the 50 breeding lines evaluated for thrips resistance, 17 lines exhibited high levels of resistance (see table). □

Resistance to thrips in breeding lines derived from *O. officinalis*.

Breeding line	Damage rating ^a
IR54742-1-20-10-11-2	1.0 a
IR54742-4-7-9-7-1	1.0 a
IR54742-6-1-14-15-1	1.0 a
IR54742-6-1-14-15-3	1.0 a
IR54742-6-20-9-3-1	1.0 a
IR54742-6-20-9-3-2	1.0 a
IR54742-6-34-17-11-1	1.0 a
IR54742-18-17-20-15-2	1.0 a
IR54742-22-14-24-22-2	1.0 a
IR54742-22-14-24-22-3	1.0 a
IR54742-22-19-3-7-1	1.0 a
IR54742-22-19-3-7-2	1.0 a
IR54742-22-19-3-7-3	1.0 a
IR54742-33-18-20-3-5	1.0 a
IR54742-52-10-17-8-1	1.0 a
Ptb 21	1.0 a
TN1	9.0 b

^aMean of 5 replications. Scored using the *Standard evaluation system for rice* (0.9). Means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT.

Reaction of summer and winter rice cultivars to hispa in Assam, India

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Hispa *Dicladispa armigera* (Oliv.) (Coleoptera: Chrysomelidae) is a serious endemic rice pest in Assam. Fifty ahu (summer) rice cultivars from the Regional Agricultural Research Station, Titabor, Assam, were grown for 1 yr in earthen pots (40 cm diam, 36 cm deep) to screen for hispa resistance.

Pots containing ten 30-d-old seedlings each were randomly spaced at 20 × 15 cm in a 10-m² area surrounded by a white, mosquito-proof nylon net (15 × 15 × 2.5 m). Each cultivar had four replications (pots). About 14,000 field-collected adults were starved for 8 h and then released inside the net at 10/plant.

Saket 4 and Culture 1 were used as susceptible checks for summer and winter rice. Percent hispa-damaged leaves were recorded on three plants randomly selected from each replication of each variety 48 h after Saket-4 suffered 100% leaf damage.

Saket 4, Ratna, recommended modern varieties in Assam, and Culture 1 suffered more than 90% leaf damage. Eleven entries were moderately resistant

Reaction of summer and winter rice cultivars to hispa under nethouse conditions. Jorhat, Assam, India.

Variety	Leaf damage ^a (%)
<i>Summer rice</i>	
As 75	12.8
As 48	14.2
Govind	14.6
Bijer 3	15.0
Bengaubisi	15.1
As 36	16.5
Gareni	16.8
As 36/20	17.1
As 93/1	18.1
As 36/14	18.5
Mala	19.6
<i>Winter rice</i>	
Boro 1	12.5
IET10896	14.2
Govind	15.4
IET10898	15.9
IET10895	16.9

^aAv of 1989 and 1990.

with 11-20% leaf damage and could be used as donors (see table). Mala and Govind were high yielding and may be recommended for hispa endemic areas.

Seventeen boro (winter) rice cultivars were similarly screened under nethouse conditions. Five had 12- 17% leaf damage.

Nonpreference for feeding may be the resistance mechanism in the varieties tested. □

Field screening of rice cultivars for resistance to gall midge (GM) *Orseolia oryzae*

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GM is a major rice pest of increasing incidence in southern Tamil Nadu. Severe incidence of silver shoot caused by GM has been observed in Chengalpattu-MGR district during Aug on sornavari (Apr-May to Aug-Sep) rices and during Nov-Dec on late samba (Aug-Sep to Jan-Feb) crops.

We drew 100 entries from five variety trials during 1991 sornavari: 12th International Irrigated Rice Yield Nursery (IIRYN) (17), Multilocation Trial I (MLTI) (7), Preliminary Variety Trial (PVT) (24), Hybrid Rice Trial (HRT) (2), and 16th International Rice Stem Borer Nursery (IRSBN) (50). The entries were evaluated for GM resistance in replicated field trials at RRS, Chengalpattu-MGR district. Popular varieties ADT36, ADT37, and IR50 were

Varietal screening for GM resistance. RRS, Tirur, India, 1991-92.

Entries	Source	Total entries (no.)	Silver shoots (%)	Score
BG1165-2	IIRYN		2.3	3
ASD17	PVT		3.0	3
SR26 B	IRSBN		3.3	3
BG850-2	IIRYN		3.7	3
BG367-4	IRSBN		4.3	3
W 1263	IRSBN		4.5	3
CO 29	PVT		5.0	3
SPR7477-7-2-1	IRSBN		5.0	3
3 cultures	PVT)	14	6.3 to	5
11 cultures	IRSBN)		10.0	
2 hybrid rices	HRT)	78	11.1 to	7-9
7 cultures	MLT I)		50.0	
19 cultures	PVT)			
15 cultures	IIRYN)			
35 cultures	IRSBN)			
ADT36 (standard)			14.3	7
ADT37 (standard)			9.1	5
IR50 (standard)			16.7	7
MDU3 (resistant check)			4.5	3
TKM9 (susceptible check)			32.3	9

standards; MDU3 was the resistant check and TKM9 the susceptible check.

Environmental conditions favored GM infestation; 30-50% silver shoots were observed on TKM9 (see table). Entries were scored for silver shoot at maximum tillering using the *Standard evaluation system for rice* (1988) 0-9 scale.

Virulence of brown planthopper (BPH) in Vietnam

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We evaluated the 1990 International Rice Brown Planthopper Nursery in Hanoi (northern Vietnam) and Tien Giang (southern Vietnam) for BPH resistance.

Test insects were field-collected BPH reared in the greenhouse. We sowed seeds of entries in seedboxes and then infested 7-d-old seedlings with second- to third-instar nymphs. All

BG1165-2, ASD17, SR26B, BG850-2, BG367-4, W1263, CO 29, and SPR7477-7-2-1 were moderately resistant, with 2.3-5.0% silver shoot incidence. Fourteen cultures were moderately susceptible, and the remaining 78 entries were susceptible with 11.1-50.0% silver shoots. □

entries were rated for damage using the *Standard evaluation system for rice* when susceptible check plants had died.

Of 110 entries, 36% exhibited resistance in Hanoi and 4% in Tien Giang. The BPH population in Hanoi was considered biotype 2 because it damaged Mudgo and IR26 (both with *Bph 1* resistance gene) but did not damage ASD7, IR36, or CR94-13 (all with *bph 2* gene) (see table). Varieties in Tien Giang possessing *Bph 1* and *bph 2* and Babawee (*bph 4*) were susceptible.

Neither population damaged Rathu Heenati (*Bph 3*) or Ptb 33. This indicates that the BPH population in Tien Giang was more virulent than the Hanoi population and would endanger the popular cultivars being planted in Mekong Delta. □

Reactions of selected varieties to BPH populations in Hanoi and Tien Giang, Vietnam.

Variety	Resistance gene or origin	Damage rating ^a by BPH populations in	
		Hanoi	Tien Giang
Mudgo	<i>Bph 1</i>	MS	S
IR26	<i>Bph 1</i>	S	S
ASD7	<i>bph 2</i>	R	S
IR36	<i>bph 2</i>	R	S
CR94-13	<i>bph 2</i>	R	S
Rathu Heenati	<i>Bph 3</i>	R	R
Babawee	<i>bph 4</i>	R	MS
RP1579-28-54	India	R	S
Chianung Shen yu 26	Taiwan	MR	S
Milyang 54	Korea	MR	S
IR25587-133-3-2-2-2	IRRI	R	S
IR28222-9-22-2-2	IRRI	R	S
IR31802-48-2-2-2	IRRI	R	S
TN1 (susceptible check)	-	S	S
Ptb 33 (resistant check)	-	R	R

^a Scored using *Standard evaluation system for rice*. R = resistant, MR = moderately resistant, S = susceptible, MS = moderately susceptible.